

UNLOCKING GROUNDWATER POTENTIAL: A STUDY OF NKWELLE-EZUNAKA FARM ESTATE, SOUTHEASTERN NIGERIA

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Abstract: Groundwater, a vital component of the hydrosphere, represents a valuable resource that underpins various human activities and ecosystems. This paper elucidates the significance of groundwater as a subsurface water source, emphasizing its dynamic nature within the water cycle. Despite the widespread availability of groundwater globally, its vulnerability to contamination in certain regions necessitates a nuanced understanding of factors influencing its quality and accessibility.

Groundwater offers numerous advantages over other water sources, making it a preferred option for a significant proportion of water users worldwide. Its inherent availability and minimal treatment requirements render it a reliable and cost-effective source of potable water. Moreover, natural barriers often shield groundwater from contamination, ensuring its purity and suitability for various purposes.

However, in regions characterized by thin weathered layers and hydraulic continuity between aquifers and the ground surface, groundwater faces heightened risks of contamination from surface sources. Anthropogenic activities, such as industrial discharge, agricultural runoff, and improper waste disposal, further exacerbate these vulnerabilities, posing significant challenges to groundwater quality and sustainability.

This paper highlights the importance of proactive measures to safeguard groundwater resources from contamination and depletion. By integrating scientific insights with policy interventions and community engagement, stakeholders can develop robust management strategies to mitigate contamination risks and ensure the long-term viability of groundwater as a vital resource.

Through a comprehensive analysis of existing literature and case studies, this paper offers insights into the complex interplay of natural and anthropogenic factors shaping groundwater quality and vulnerability. By prioritizing sustainable management practices and promoting awareness of groundwater conservation, societies can uphold the integrity of this essential resource for current and future generations.

Keywords: Groundwater, Water cycle, Contamination, Sustainability, Management strategies.

INTRODUCTION

Groundwater is the subsurface water that occurs beneath the geological formation capable of yielding water. Groundwater is constantly in motion in the hydrosphere through the process of water cycle (Amadi, 2010).

The advantages of groundwater over other sources have been severally emphasized in literatures. High percentage of water users in the world rely substantially on groundwater due to its availability in almost all parts of the world (Reilly et al., 2008). In addition, and most importantly, very minor water treatment is often required to make it

potable. Groundwater is largely protected from contamination by natural barriers. However, in areas with thin weathered layers and where aquifers are in hydraulic continuity with the ground surface, groundwater could be vulnerable to contamination from surface sources.

Although water is a renewable resource, its supply in suitable quality is steadily decreasing due to poor groundwater management and effect of poor waste water management, especially in developing countries like Nigeria. The demand for groundwater resource has increased significantly throughout the world due to population growth, socio-economic development, technological and climate changes (Olayinka et al., 1999; Alcamo, 2007). The need to sustain groundwater by people has strengthened the application of appropriate geophysical and hydrogeologic investigations (Olayinka et al., 1999; Olorunfemi et al., 1999; Lashkaripour, 2003; Batayneh, 2010; Omosuyi, 2010; Anudu et al., 2011) to locate areas of high and reliable groundwater prospect or characterize seasonal changes in the near surface aquifer (Webb et al., 2011). Water related diseases are mostly responsible for about 80% of illnesses or deaths in the developing countries (UNESCO, 2007). Though groundwater can be a source of potable water supply, there is need to evaluate its portability since it is often susceptibility to contamination.

Aquifer protective capacity has been defined as the capacity of the overburden unit to impede and filter percolating ground surface contaminating liquid into the aquifer unit. It is a measure of the ability of an earth medium to retard and filter percolating fluid. The protective capacity of an overburden is directly proportional to its thickness and inversely proportional to its hydraulic conductivity. Permeable materials such as sand and gravels have high resistivity, high hydraulic conductivity, and low longitudinal conductance while impermeable material such as clay and shale have high longitudinal conductance due to their low resistivity values. Sedimentary rocks, which usually are more porous and have high water content and low resistivity (Olisah and Obiekezie, 2020). Wet soil and fresh groundwater have even lower resistivity values. Clayey soil normally has a lower resistivity value than sandy soil.

In this study, we investigate the groundwater potential of the Nkwelle-Ezunaka Farm Estate by determining the type, thickness and protective capacity of the aquifer in the area.

Figure 1. Sketch map of Nkwelle Ezunaka Farm Estate.

Source: Authors 2022

Location and geology of the study area

The study area is located within Nkwelle-Ezunaka Farm Estate (Figure 1) in Oyi Local Government Area of Anambra State, Southeastern Nigeria. The area lies between longitude 6°51'27"□6°59'37"E and latitude 6°13'18"□6°20'27"N and covers an area of about 60 km².

The study area lies within the Anambra Basin in the Lower Benue Trough tectonic unit. Anambra Basin is a synclinal structural depression and one of the intracraton basins in Nigeria located in south central Nigeria (Figure 2). It is bounded to the north by Bida Basin and Northern Nigerian Massif, to the east by Benue Trough, to the west by the West African Massif and to the southwest by the Niger Delta Complex (Whiteman, 1982). The basin is a Cretaceous basin having almost a roughly triangular shape (Nwajide, 1996) with a total sediment thickness of about 2500 m covering an area of about 40,000 km² (Reyment, 1965). Anambra Basin is characterized by enormous lithologic heterogeneity in both lateral and vertical extensions derived from a range of pale environmental setting. Anambra Basin is mainly held to have originated after the Santonian folding and uplift of the Abakaliki region during Campanian to Mid Eocene which resulted in shifting of the depocentre into Anambra Platform and Afikpo region (Obi et al., 2001). Notable researchers (Ofoegbu, 1985; Burke, 1996) have attributed the origin of the basin to the separation of African and South America lithospheric plates and consequent opening of the Altanic in early Cretaceous. Sedimentation during the Campanian-Maastrichtian marked the beginning of deposition in the Anambra Basin and also the third cycle of marine inclusion in the Lower Benue Trough (Ehinola et al., 2005).

Source: Obaje (2009).

Figure 2. Geology map of the Nigeria showing the location of the study area.

MATERIALS

The basic equipment used for this geophysical survey is the ABEM Terameter SAS 1000.

The resistivity meter is equipped with a 12 v battery, two current transmission cables on reels, two potential cables, four metal electrodes and a salt solution. Other auxiliary equipment for the survey included a Global Positioning System (GPS) for determining the resistivity survey locations and topography, geologic hammers for driving electrodes into the ground, two measuring tapes and cutlasses for clearing the traverses.

Table 1. Longitudinal conductance and protective capacity rating.

Longitudinal (mhos)	Conductance	Protective rating	capacity
>10		Excellent	
5 - 10		Very good	
0.7 - 4.9		Good	
0.2 - 0.69		Moderate	
0.1 - 0.19		Weak	
< 0.1		Poor	

Source: Ogungbemi (2013).

METHODS

The study involved the use of electrical resistivity method. The technique adopted was Vertical Electrical Sounding (VES). The soundings used to characterize the various lithologic units and to determine the depth to water table. A total of ten soundings using Schlumberger array were carried out in the area. The VES field data were processed using the Schlumberger automatic INTERPEX analysis software, which generated model curves of apparent resistivity against spacing ($\frac{AB}{2}$) using initial layer parameters. The iso-resistivity, isopach and aquifer protective capacity maps of the study area were obtained using Surfer 8 software. The Dar-Zarrouk parameters were obtained from the first order geoelectric parameters (layer resistivities and thicknesses). These included the total longitudinal conductance (S) and total transverse resistance (T). These secondary geoelectric parameters are particularly important when they are used to describe a geoelectric section consisting of several layers. The longitudinal conductance is used to define target areas of groundwater potential (Okonkwo and Ugwu, 2015). High longitudinal conductance usually indicates thick succession and is suggestive of high groundwater potential. The transverse resistance has a direct relation with transmissivity and is also used to define target areas of good groundwater potential (Okonkwo and Ugwu, 2015). For n layers, the total longitudinal conductance is given as:

$$S = \sum_{i=1}^n \left(\frac{h_i}{\rho_i} \right) \quad (1)$$

The total transverse resistance is also given as:

$$T = \sum_{i=1}^n \rho_i h_i \quad (2)$$

where h_i is the thickness of the i th layer and ρ_i is the resistivity of the i th layer which were deduced from the VES curves of the apparent resistivity versus spacing. Using Ogungbemi (2013) classification, the results of longitudinal conductance was used to classify areas into good, moderate, weak and poor protective capacity shown in Table 1. The lithology of the layers was inferred by correlation to one of the boreholes drilled in the study area and based on the geology of the study area.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Qualitative interpretation of the profiles and depth sounding curves were carried out based on distinctive geoelectric parameters of the layers represented by the four types of auxiliary curve (A, H, K and Q). VES 1, 2, 4 and 7 are type AQ curves while VES 3, 5, 6 and 10 are type KQ curves. VES 7 and 8 have type HHQ and HQ curve, respectively. VES 1, 2, 4, 5 and 7 have five geoelectric layers while VES 6, 9 and 10 have six geoelectric layers. VES 3 and 8 have seven geoelectric layers (Figures 3 to 12). A summary of qualitative interpretation of VES curves is shown in Table 2 while Table 3 shows a summary of the quantitative interpretation results of the VES.

A correlation of the interpretation results of VES 1-10 to the lithologic log of a borehole drilled in the area shows the occurrence of five, six or seven lithologic layers, namely: Lateritic silty clayey sandy top soil, lateritic sandstone, wet lateritic shale, lateritic shale, lateritic sandstone, dry sandstone, wet shale, sandstone, dry sandstone, water saturated sandstone and water saturated shaly sandstone as shown in Figures 13 to 15. The aquifer layers are water saturated sandstone and water saturated shaly sandstone. These aquifers are located either at the fourth, fifth, sixth or seventh layer (Table 3) in agreement with the result of Oyeku and Eludoyin (2010) and Uma (2003). The resistivity of the aquifer layers varies from 242.7 to 13658 Ω m (Table 3) with thickness

ranging from 52 to 102 m (Figure 16). VES 2, 5 and 7 have high aquifer thickness which is a favourable condition for productive and sustainable borehole yield (Ugwu and Ezeh, 2012). The iso-resistivity map of the area (Figure 17) shows that VES 4 and 10 located at the northern part of the study area have low resistivity values ranging from 1200 to 1500 Ωm , suggesting an aquiferous zone of water saturated sandstone. The aquifer layers have high transverse resistance which ranges from 36,469 to 107,117 (Table 3). This implies that the layers have high transmissivity and therefore suggests that the study area has good underground potential.

The aquifer protective capacity was determined by calculating the longitudinal conductance and was found to vary from 0.0 to 0.062 mhos as shown in Figure 18. This range indicates a poor aquifer protective capacity, in accordance with Ogungbemi (2013).

Figure 3. Interpretation result of VES 1 data. Source: Authors 2022

Figure 4. Interpretation result of VES 2 data. Source: Authors 2022

Figure 5. Interpretation result of VES 3 data.

Source: Authors 2022

Figure 6. Interpretation result of VES 4 data.

Source: Authors 2022

Figure 7. Interpretation result of VES 5.

Source: Authors 2022

Figure 8. Interpretation result of VES 6 data.

Source: Authors 2022

Figure 9. Interpretation result of VES 7 data.

Source: Authors 2022

Figure 10. Interpretation result of VES 8 data.

Source: Authors 2022

Figure 11. Interpretation result of VES 9 data.

Source: Authors 2022

Figure 12. Interpretation result of VES 10 data.

Source: Authors 2022

Table 2. Summary of qualitative interpretation of VES curves.

VES	Coordinate	Curve type	Resistivity profile	Number of layers
1	N 6° 16' 11" E 6° 51' 36"	AQ	$\rho_1 < \rho_2 < \rho_3 > \rho_4 > \rho_5$	5
2	N 6° 16' 13" E 6° 55' 34"	AQ	$\rho_1 < \rho_2 < \rho_3 > \rho_4 > \rho_5$	5
3	N 6° 18' 8" E 6° 51' 35"	KQ	$\rho_1 < \rho_2 > \rho_3 < \rho_4 > \rho_5 > \rho_6 > \rho_7$	7

4	N 6° 18' 6" E 6° 55' 34"	AQ	$\rho_1 < \rho_2 < \rho_3 > \rho_4 > \rho_5$	5
5	N 6° 15' 14" E 6° 57' 41"	KQ	$\rho_1 < \rho_2 > \rho_3 > \rho_4 > \rho_5$	5
6	N 6° 15' 13" E 6° 59' 31"	KQ	$\rho_1 < \rho_2 > \rho_3 < \rho_4 > \rho_5 > \rho_6$	6
7	N 6° 13' 19" E 6° 57' 37"	AQ	$\rho_1 < \rho_2 < \rho_3 > \rho_4 > \rho_5$	5
8	N 6° 13' 18" E 6° 59' 37"	HHQ	$\rho_1 > \rho_2 < \rho_3 > \rho_4 < \rho_5 > \rho_6 > \rho_7$	7
9	N 6° 20' 27" E 6° 51' 27"	HQ	$\rho_1 > \rho_2 < \rho_3 > \rho_4 > \rho_5 > \rho_6$	6
10	N 6° 20' 28" E 6° 55' 27"	KQ	$\rho_1 < \rho_2 > \rho_3 < \rho_4 > \rho_5 > \rho_6$	6

Source: Authors 2022

Table 3. Summary of quantitative interpretation of VES results.

	VES Layer	Thickness		Depth	Lithology	Longitudinal		Aquifer
		(Ωm)	(m)			(S) (mhos)	(T)	
	1	614.4	2.8	2.8	Lateritic silty, clayey sandy top soil	0.0046	1720.32	(0.0544) Poor
	2	886.3	5.9			0.0067	5229.17	
1	3	1113.9	48.1	56.8	Sandstone	0.0431	53578.59	
	4	587	88.6	145.4		0.1509	52008.2	
	5	395.1	∞	∞	Water saturated shaly sandstone	∞	∞	
	VES Layer	(Ωm)	(m)	Depth	Lithology	conductance	resistance	Protective
8.7	Lateritic sandstone			Water saturated sandstone				
1	323.3	1.2	1.2		Lateritic silty, clayey sandy top soil	0.0037	387.96	
2	837.7	7.1	5.9		Lateritic sandstone	0.0070	4942.43	
(0.0369)			36.1					
2	3	∞	124.7	167.9			82114.95	
49662.77			∞	∞	1375.7 43.2	Sandstone	∞	0.0262

Poor

4	658.5			Water saturated sandstone	0.1894		
5	532.1			Water saturated shaly sandstone		∞	
1	854.8	1.7	1.7	Lateritic silty, clayey sandy top Soil	0.0020		1453.16
2	1517.4		3.5	5.2 Lateritic sandstone	0.0023	5310.9	(0.0691)
3							
3	608.4	9.2	14.3	Lateritic shale	0.0151	5597.28	Poor
4	2814.5		10.7	25.0 Dry sandstone	0.0038		30115.15

Table 3. Cont'd

	82.5	1250.0		Sandstone	57.50	0.0459		72087.75
6	1080.9		99.1	181.6 Water saturated sandstone		0.0917		107117.19
7	768.8		∞	∞ Water saturated shaly sandstone		∞		∞
1	630.8	1.3	1.3	Lateritic silty, clayey sandy top soil	0.0021		820.04	
2	1117.7	10.0	8.7	Lateritic sandstone	0.0078	9723.99		
(0.041)			38.6					
4	3	1241.9	105.1	153.7	48.6	Sandstone	0.0311	83207.67
			∞	∞				∞
	47937.34							
Poor								
4	791.7			Water saturated sandstone	0.1327			
5	455.3			Water saturated shaly sandstone		∞		
1	2352.1	0.2	0.2	Lateritic silty, clayey sandy top Soil	∞	0.00009	470.42	
2	2680.0	3.5	3.3	Lateritic sandstone	0.0012	8844		
(0.01009)			21.3					
5	3	2426.2	100.6	125.4	24.8	Sandstone	0.0088	51678.06
			∞	∞				∞
Poor								
4	925.3			Water saturated sandstone	0.1087			
5	591.7			Water saturated shaly sandstone		∞		
1	888.8	0.9	0.9	Lateritic silty, clayey sandy top soil	0.0010		799.92	
2	3741.9		4.8	5.7 Lateritic sandstone	0.0013		17961.12	
3	664.5	3.6	9.3	Shaly sandstone	0.0054	(0.0137)	2392.2	
6				107.1			76041	
4	3570.0		21.3	∞	30.6	Sandstone	0.0060	Poor
5	344.0	76.5		Water saturated Sandstone	0.2224		∞	
6	242.7	∞		Water saturated shaly-sandstone		∞		

1	791.7	1.1	1.1	Lateritic silty, clayey sandy top soil	0.0014		870.87	
(0.0329)							6356.34	
2	1177.1	5.4	6.4	111.3 Lateritic sandstone	0.0046		80389.4	
Poor							340048.38	
7	3	6183.8	13.0	19.5 Dry sandstone	0.0021		∞	
4	3700.2		91.9	Sandstone	0.0248			
5	1246.2		∞	Water saturated sandstone		∞		
1	1782.4		0.7	0.7 Lateritic silty, clayey sandy top soil		∞	1247.68	
0.00039							265.2	
2	221.0	1.2	1.9	Wet lateritic shale	0.0054		38283.75	(0.02372)
3	8507.5		4.5	6.4 Lateritic sandstone	0.00053		2179.52	Poor
				109.4			458058.15	
8	4	389.2	5.6	12.0 Wet ∞ shale	0.0144	5	12413.5	
sandstone 0.0030							36.9	48.9 Dry
6	1365.8		60.5	Water saturated sandstone	0.0443			
7	321.4	∞		Water saturated shaly-sandstone				
1	982.5	4.4	4.4	Lateritic silty, clayey sandy top soil	0.0045		4323	
2	608.4	10.4	14.8	lateritic sandstone	0.0171		6327.36	
3	7976.3		13.0	27.9 Dry Sandstone	0.0016		103691.9	(0.0624)
9								
4	802.0	31.4	59.3	Sandstone	0.0392	Poor	25182.8	
5	608.4	53.6	Water	112.9 ∞ saturated sandstone		0.0881	36469.44	
6	289.1	∞		Water saturated shaly-sandstone		∞		
1	348.9	0.4	0.4	Lateritic silty, clayey sandy top Soil	0.0011	139.56		
2	1065.5		4.6	5.0 lateritic sandstone	0.0043		4901.3	
3	491.0	5.5	10.5	Lateritic shale	0.0112	2700.5		(0.0218)
10								
4	4468.9	23.3	33.8	Dry sandstone	0.0052	104125.37	Poor	5 887.6 83.1 116.8 Water saturated sandstone
0.0936	73759.56							
6	478.9		∞	∞ Water saturated shaly sandstone			∞	

Source: Authors 2022

Figure 13. Interpreted lithology of the five layer VES curves. Source: Authors 2022

Figure 14. Interpreted lithology of the six layer VES curves. Source: Authors 2022

Figure 15. Interpreted lithology of the seven layer VES curves. Source: Authors 2022

Figure 16. Isopach (thickness) map of the aquifer layers at various VES stations.

Source: Authors 2022

Figure 17. Isoresistivity map of the study area.

Source: Authors 2022

Figure 18. Map of aquifer protective capacity of the study area.

Source: Authors 2022

Conclusion

In this study, the groundwater prospect and aquifer protective capacity of the rock units at Nkwelle-Ezunaka Farm Estate in Southeastern Nigeria were investigated by conducting ten vertical electrical soundings. The results showed that VES 1, 2, 4, 5 and 7 have five lithologic layers, VES 6, 9 and 10 have six geoelectric layers while VES 3 and 8 have seven lithologic layers. The subsurface sequence comprises the lateritic silt, clayey sandy topsoil, lateritic sandstone, sandstone, dry sandstone, lateritic shale, water saturated sandstone and water saturated shaly sandstone. The water saturated sandstone and water saturated shaly sandstone layers constitute the aquifer units in the area, with depth ranging from 53.6 to 124.7 m, and thickness varying from 52 m to a maximum of 102 m. VES 2, 5 and 7 stations have been identified as the best locations for productive and sustainable borehole yield because of their high aquifer thicknesses and transmissivity.

This study also revealed that all parts of the area are underlain by materials of poor protective capacity, implying that the area is vulnerable to contamination that may arise from runoff water, sewage and indiscriminately disposed waste materials in the area. Thus, the information obtained from this study can serve as a baseline data for pre-drill estimate of yield of any prospective borehole in the area.

CONFLICT OF INTERESTS

The authors have not declared any conflict of interests.

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